

ICT Fluency among the Women Teacher Educators

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Introduction

The junction of computer and information technologies is rapidly altering the very fabric of human lives. It is changing the way people meet, socialize, communicate, and work. Information and communication technologies can be powerful tools for advancing economic and social development through the formation of new sorts of economic activity, employment openings, improvements in education and other services, and the increase of networking, participation and encouragement within society.

Information Technology is the acquisition, processing, storage, and dissemination of vocal, pictorial, textual, and numerical information by a microelectronics-based combination of computing and telecommunications.

In the context of Indian Education, the nation has to decide its future directions. Information technology has ushered in unprecedented changes in the industrial and business sectors and education can no longer alienate itself from influence of computer technology .

Women and ICT

A large group of workingwomen of India is in the rural and unorganized sectors. Socially the majorities of Indian women are still tradition bound and are in a disadvantageous position.

More women are involved in careers in the communications sector, but few have attained positions at the decision-making level or serve on governing boards and bodies that influence media policy. The lack of gender sensitivity in the media is evidenced by the failure to eliminate the gender-based stereotyping that can be found in public and private local, national and international media organizations. The continued projection of negative and degrading images of women in mass communications - electronic, print, visual and audio - must be changed. Print and electronic media in most countries do not provide a balanced picture of women's diverse lives and contributions to society in a changing world. In addition, violent and degrading or pornographic media products [are also negatively affecting] women and their participation in society.

Information Technology

For the purpose of the present study, Information Technology is defined as the use of hardware and software for efficient management of information i.e., storage, retrieval, processing, communication, diffusion and sharing of information for social, economic and cultural upliftment.

Information Technology Fluency

‘Fluency with Information Technology’ is the acquisition of three types of Information Technology knowledge.

It consists of three dimensions namely Information Technology Skills, Information Technology Concepts and Information Technology Intellectual Capabilities.

1. Information Technology Skills refer to proficiency with contemporary applications such as browsing, e-mail, word processing, etc.
2. Information Technology Concepts refer to foundational ideas related to computer and internet.
3. Information Technology Intellectual Capabilities refer to higher-level thinking abilities such as logical reasoning, problem solving, complexity management, etc., related to Information Technology.

Women Teacher Educator

‘Women Teacher Educator’ means any regular women teacher of B.Ed. and M.Ed. College which is a government, self-finance, or autonomous institution and is coming under Tamilnadu Teacher Education University (TNTEU).

Methodology in Brief

A research design is the arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with economy in procedure. In fact, the research design is the conceptual structure within which research is conducted; it constitutes the blueprint for the collection, measurement and analysis of data

Descriptive Research method, using Survey Technique was adopted for the present study. The present study targets the Women teacher educators working in the B.Ed. and M.Ed. colleges coming under the Tamilnadu Teacher Education University (TNTEU) in Madurai. Women Teacher Educators were selected from 29 colleges of education for the Macro-study using Random sampling technique. The sample was selected from a listing of all the teacher educators in each teacher education institution of the three districts in a number form and 100 women teacher educators were chosen by the Kendall and Smith Table of Random Sampling Numbers.

Data Analysis

The data collected through the above tools were subjected to the following types of descriptive, inferential, and qualitative data analysis.

Findings of the Study

Results of the data analysis pertaining to the present survey are summarized as below:

1. Level of IT Fluency of the women teacher educators is found to be significantly related to the variables like Locale, Technical qualification, Educational qualification, Subject specialization, and Exposure to computer and internet.
2. Level of IT Fluency of the women teacher educators is found to be related to the demographic variables like age, faculty variables like teaching experience and other institutional variables.

3. Field Visit and Observation of the Colleges of Education taken for micro-level analysis throw light on the factors which are conducive and detrimental to high IT fluency among Women Teacher Educators.

Suggestions and Recommendations

A multi- pronged strategy has to be evolved by Policy makers and Educational administrators together to overcome the problem of low ICT fluency. Necessary curricular modifications in the pre-service teacher education curriculum, organizing sufficient number of in-service capacity development programmes to enhance their Information Technology Fluency, and providing adequate IT infrastructure in all teacher education institutions are the immediate need of the hour.

Locale was found to be significantly related to the level of Information Technology Fluency of the women teacher educators with the rural and semi-urban teachers having low level of Information Technology Fluency. Hence, rural and semi-urban areas have to be given required attention to accelerate their Information Technology Fluency.

All women teacher educators irrespective of their disciplines, should be given the needed training, in the Information Technology related Skills. They should be motivated and encouraged to utilize modern technological gadgets in the teaching-learning process. Technically not qualified respondents are found to be having a low level Information Technology. Incentives in terms of awards/increments should be given to the teacher educators who practice Information Technology in their class rooms at a higher level.

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